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D5.5: Report on demonstration at Demosite3: Almendralejo

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Deliverable Development and Review Process

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Executive summary

Project Ô Deliverable 5.5 aims to document the final validation of the Demosite 3 sited in Almendralejo, Spain. The location preparation, installation of the pilot plant and their operation was described in previous documents of the project, so, in this section, a global review of the technologies and methodologies proposed, most relevant data collection, results derived from those data, and an analysis of the KPIs in relation with the Demosite 3 is described.

The Deliverable 5.5 stems from Work Package 5 (**WP5**): *Demonstration of small loop of water recycling within a complex system*, specifically in Task **T5.3**: *Technological demonstration activities on pilot modules*. In this sense, a summary of the selected location for Demosite 3, Almendralejo, has been addressed, together with the most relevant conditions of the area, characteristics of the input water and challenges and opportunities of the selected location for Demosite 3 implantation.

The proposed technological solution to address the challenges detected in the metropolitan area of Almendralejo (Demosite 3) involves of a modular treatment system that integrates three different units, known as **Mobile3Tech**, for the elimination of contaminants and quality improvement of treated water, enabling its safe reuse. The main goal of Demosite 3 is to incorporate abatement processes aimed at spill treatment and emerging pollutant elimination, together with a continuous monitoring system which discerns if there is a presence of industrial spills or not.

In this demonstrator report, the train of technologies included in **Mobile3Tech** has been defined:

- Advanced adsorption system using granular activated carbon (GAC) for the removal of emerging pollutants in order to improve the quality of treated water and to ensure its reuse. This is complemented with powder active carbon, added in specific stages of water treatment at the pilot.
- Advanced oxidation treatment, a photo-Fenton process, for the regeneration of the saturated activated carbon, following the main circular economy principles of reutilization by eliminating a potential waste which become functional again after oxidation treatment.
- Advanced control unit. Continuous monitoring of pollutants detected at different WWTP sampling points in order to detect industrial spills and avoid biological damage by diverting the discharge to the **Mobile3Tech** system.

The Deliverable 5.5 explains the main characteristics of each described technology, daily operating cost of the process and a testing report with operating plan details, ensuring the validation of the technology train at Demosite 3.

A resume of the data obtained in filtration with GAC module, regeneration using Photo-Fenton process and assays in toxic detection module provided by Technion has been reported in this document. This Data collection allows to demonstrate the feasibility of the technology train proposed and to assess performance according to the KPIs proposed in Project Ô.

Table of Contents

Deliverable Development and Review Process	2
Executive summary.....	3
List of Figures	5
Abbreviations	5
1 Introduction.....	6
2 Demosite 3: ALMENDRALEJO	7
2.1 Location of the Demosite 3	7
2.2 Why the Demosite 3 was chosen.....	7
2.3 Characteristics of the input water	9
2.4 Introduction of the selected train of technologies.....	12
3 The Mobile3Tech module.....	14
3.1 Filtration with granular activated carbon module	15
3.2 Regeneration of granular activated carbon	16
3.3 Advanced control unit	17
4 Testing report.....	18
4.1 Testing campaign description.....	18
4.1.1 Filtration with granular activated carbon.....	18
4.1.2 Regeneration of granular activated carbon.....	19
4.1.3 Advanced control unit	20
4.2 Data report.....	21
4.2.1 Filtration with granular activated carbon.....	21
4.2.2 Regeneration of the granular activated carbon.....	23
4.2.3 Advanced control unit	25
5 Conclusions	26

List of Figures

Figure 1. Almendralejo location	7
Figure 2. General scheme for Almendralejo WWTP	7
Figure 3. General scheme of WWTP of Almendralejo with Mobile3Tech integration.....	13
Figure 4. Scheme of the Mobile3tech unit deployed at the WWTP of	14
Figure 5: Final appearance of Mobile3Tech module	15
Figure 6. Advanced adsorption filter (GAC).....	16
Figure 7. Details of advanced oxidation unit (Photo-Fenton).....	17
Figure 8. Advanced control unit module for toxicity detection (Advanced control unit).....	18
Figure 9. Mobile3Tech testing schedule.....	Errore. Il segnalibro non è definito.
Figure 10. Conversion values of Tramadol removal at different sampling dates	22
Figure 11. BET surfaces of regeneration assays at different conditions	24
Figure 12. Toxicity detection (%) vs Conductivity at advanced control unit.....	25

List of Tables

Table 1. Average values of input and output water physicochemical and microbiological composition of the Almendralejo WWTP (2017 data).	10
Table 2. VOCs analysed at input water of the Almendralejo WWTP.....	10
Table 3. Minimum requirements for general effluent discharges according to Council Directive 91/271/EEC and Regulation (EU) 2020/741	11
Table 4. Technical specifications of filtration module.....	16
Table 5. Technical specifications of Photo-Fenton module.....	17
Table 6. Analytic parameters – Sampling for filtration with GAC module.....	19
Table 7. Dates when the samples were collected	19
Table 8. Trial variables and sampling of Photo-Fenton module	20
Table 9. Analytic parameters for advanced control unit.....	20
Table 10. Range of conversion values and average conversion values (%) of parameters analysed at Mobile3Tech module: filtration with GAC.....	22

Abbreviations

BOD₅: Biological Oxygen Demand (5 days)
BET: Brunauer, Emmet and Teller method
CFU: Colony forming units
COD: Chemical Oxygen Demand
DWTP: Drinking Water Treatment Plant
GC: Genome copies
H₂SO₄: sulfuric acid
H₂O₂: Hydrogen Peroxide
KPIs: Key Performance Indicators
N-NH₄: ammoniac nitrogen
N-NO₃: nitrate nitrogen
P-PO₄: phosphate phosphorous
SS: Suspended Solids
TOC: Total Organic Carbon
WWTP: Wastewater Treatment Plant

1 Introduction

Water is an integral element in all systems, essential for the maintenance and development of different biological processes. Due to its unique properties, humans have exploited water resources for energy generation, industrial processes and their own sustainment, improving water quality through treatment to make it safer to drink. However, water, especially fresh water, appears as a finite resource and in the last decades, a need for rethinking water management through a circular economy framework appears as the principal challenge for water users.

Project Ô intends to pilot this circular model using accessible technologies to drive a correct management and use of water on the whole integrated water cycle. The main objective of **Project Ô** combines different concepts, involving a new water re-use scheme (integration of small water-users in the water network management), a train of water technologies (high efficiency and low cost processes), and the adoption of a modular approach.

In this sense, four different Demosites were proposed, with diverse context, climate conditions and water characteristics in order to reach specific water requirements. Each projected Demosite have been developed to solve the problems detected in each location, together with the appropriate technologies for its water treatment. Three out of four modules installed at the Demosites will be portable, the modules require low investment cost and can be easily replicated in any interested location with minimal environmental impact.

- Demosite 1: Acquedotto Pugliese, Puglia Region – Italy. Mobile desalination + advanced Oxidation Process for treating contaminated brackish groundwater.
- Demosite 2: National Center for Mariculture, Eilat - Israel. Polishing algae plant for water reuse in RAS pond + disinfected fresh water for aquaponic produced though nano-pulsed PEF, membrane distillation and advanced adsorption treatments.
- **Demosite 3: Almendralejo WWTP, Almendralejo – Spain. Mobile Advanced Absorption and Photo Fenton with advanced control unit**
- Demosite 4: Galeb, Omis – Croatia. Photocatalytic module and nanofiltration for water reuse within a textile factory

Deliverable 5.5 consists on a demonstration report of Demosite 3. The Almendralejo WWTP preparation, installation of the pilot plant and their operation was described in previous documents of the project (D5.1 and D5.2), so, in this section, only a global review of the technologies and methodologies proposed, most relevant data collection and an analysis of the KPIs in relation with the Demosite 3 is detailed.

Also, SARS-CoV-2 abatement through Mobile3Tech is addressed in this deliverable.

2 Demosite 3: ALMENDRALEJO

This section of the Deliverable describes the location of the Demosite 3, the challenges and opportunities of the area (in order to contextualise the relevance of the essays defined), and why this Demosite was selected for pilot-plant implantation. In this sense, a brief summary of the physicochemical characteristics of the input water, as well as an introduction of the technologies chosen for toxic pollutants abatement, is explained in this part of the Deliverable.

2.1 Location of the Demosite 3

Almendralejo is a city of 35,000 inhabitants sited in the south-west of Spain (**Figure 1**). The integral water cycle, including drinking water supply, sewage and wastewater treatment is managed by SOCAMEX. Due to the agricultural wealth of the area, a multitude of industries, mostly food industries related with olive collection and wine production, processing and packaging, are located in the surroundings of the municipality of Almendralejo and use the services of its WWTP,

io location

Figure 2. General scheme for Almendralejo WWTP designed for 210,000 population equivalents.

The Almendralejo treatment plant includes a lamination deposit, which works as an equalization tank, where industrial spills are retained, if necessary, and discharged smoothly to the regular treatment line. A subsequent 2 stages biological treatment, together with 2 stages decantation, complete the whole wastewater treatment process (**Figure 2**).

2.2 Why the Demosite 3 was chosen

The consensual decision to locate Demosite 3 in Almendralejo WWTP attends some opportunities for the improvement of the treatment plant technology and the main goal of solving challenges related with emerging pollutants removal and industrial spills that affects the biological treatment and, subsequently, the whole WWTP.

On one hand, the surrounding areas of Almendralejo, belonging to the Guadiana river basin, have as their main activity agriculture, being reflected in the high number of food industries in this city. Mostly dedicated to the production of olive oil and table olives, these industries cover activities of collection, processing and packaging of these high valued products. The treatment of the olives in caustic soda and their conservation in brine, can cause serious problems in Almendralejo WWTP operation, particularly at harvest time from September to March, when WWTP registers spills with specific conditions of pH and conductivity. Despite the olive industries have their own wastewater treatment plant to solve this physicochemical anomalies and ensure normal pH and conductivity values, punctual industrial discharges with the characteristics aforementioned are collected in Almendralejo WWTP, registering high TOC values and high concentrations of macronutrients and polyphenols.

Some of these contaminants are too toxic for the microorganisms of the biological treatment, and can therefore damage the entire process WWTP; this could lead, on its part, to the pollutants ending up untreated in the aquatic environment.

On the other hand, pollutants of emerging concern are becoming more and more relevant since the last few years, as more information is available about their behaviour and importance in the environment. An exhaustive analysis of the different processes used in the typical industries of the Almendralejo surroundings allowed to define the potential risks of the Demosite 3 area and thus, take measures to address them in case they occurred. A broad screening of the collected water led to identify main contaminants or group of contaminants to which it is necessary to pay attention due to their presence and recalcitrant behavior to conventional biological treatments of the WWTP:

- **Herbicides**: The importance of the agricultural activity in Demosite 3 area implied an increase in the presence of these compounds. In particular, **Terbutylazine** has been selected as a target compound whose elimination through **Mobile3Tech** is studied in this Demosite.
- **Pharmaceutical products**: A broad study of the most consumed pharmaceutical compounds in Spain has been considered, as well as the number of drug packages sold in the Almendralejo area during 2018. This, combined with the outputs of various screenings carried out on water from the WWTP, has enabled the selection of **Tramadol** and **4-Acetylaminoantipyrine** (analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties) as the target pharmaceutical compounds.
- The great number of industries in the area imply the presence of **disinfection by-products** derived from cleaning compounds authorized for that purpose. The presence of **Acetophenone**, used in perfumery and disinfection industry, acts as a precursor for other cleaning chemicals has been included in this category. Acetophenone has been selected as the most suitable choice, as the compound originally targeted (chlorhydrate of poly hexamethylene biguanide) was never found in the screenings carried out.
- **Bisphenol A** has recently been included in the list of substances of very high concern by the European Agency for Chemical Substances and Mixtures. This compound acts as an endocrine disruptor, causing harmful effects on humans. Besides, its production in large quantities for plastic-based products can cause undesirable discharges to the aquatic media. In this sense, the study of the abatement of this pollutant in Demosite 3 has also been selected.

Besides, the Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on minimum requirements for water reuse (2018) together with the Council directive 91/271/EEC, addresses the mandatory analysis and the acceptable value limits in relation to SS, BOD₅, COD, P, N, *E.coli*, turbidity and *Legionella spp.*, ensuring the quality of water discharged. Also, the Regulation (EU) 2020/741 of the European Parliament and of the Council on minimum requirements for water reuse has addressed measures for risk assessment where selected micro-contaminants need to be monitored according to the risks for specific places. The screening previously mentioned complies with the established regulation. Due to their complex nature and the seasonality of discharges, it is difficult to find a single removal technique for these compounds.

Taking into account the above, the objective to be applied in Demosite 3 is to develop a train of technologies together with a **continuous monitoring** through the whole WWTP process, in order to perform a **final elimination of target pollutants** acting as a tertiary treatment. Furthermore, in case of registering industrial spills, the mobile pilot-plant is aimed for being connected to the lamination deposit and is able to divert the input spill in order to be treated by **Mobile3Tech** beforehand, if necessary, managing it properly. In this sense, the proposed Demosite 3 also achieves one of the main objectives of Project Ô: to offer solutions to prevent and remedy pollution from industrial discharges when and where it is needed, accomplished with the implementation of a mobile pilot plant and continuous monitoring with the capability of managing the peaks of pollutant load nearer the source.

Finally, in addition to the original objectives of Demosite 3, the global emergency situation due to the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic added new goals for this module. The efficiency of **Mobile3Tech** was also performed for the **abatement of SARS-CoV-2 in wastewater** at real scale, as will be explained in the sections below.

2.3 Characteristics of the input water

Prior to the final installation of the mobile pilot-plant in Demosite 3, a complete analysis of the input water to Almendralejo WWTP was carried out, not only to know the physicochemical values and nature of the water treated by this treatment plant, but to establish the needed and appropriate technologies according to the characteristics and type of contaminants that were detected.

Physical and chemical characteristics of the input and output water (influent and effluent, respectively) were registered and measured in order to know the water matrix of Almendralejo WWTP. In addition, the Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on minimum requirements for water reuse establishes additional parameters that need to be mandatorily analyzed: BOD₅, *E.coli*, turbidity and *Legionella spp.* Samples were collected daily, but in order to simplify the information obtained, **Table 1** shows a summary with the average values of all samples accumulated for a whole year.

Table 1. Average values of input and output water physicochemical and microbiological composition of the Almendralejo WWTP (2017 data).

		INFLUENT	EFFLUENT
Conductivity	µS/cm	2260	2165
SS	mg/l	295	11
COD	mg/l	663	62
BOD ₅	mg/l	432	10
N-NO ₃	mg/l	1.04	6.95
N-NH ₄	mg/l	37.3	2.22
P-PO ₄	mg/l	22.9	0.89
Turbidity	NTU	116	-
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	CFU/100ml	1.0 x 10 ⁶	-
<i>Legionella spp.</i>	CFU/l	Not detected	-

In order to complete the input water analysis, most common volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and other biological contaminants were studied and registered at the same sampling point for Almendralejo WWTP. The list of the VOCs analysed is provided in **Table 2**.

Table 2. VOCs analysed at input water of the Almendralejo WWTP.

PARAMETER	PARAMETER
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	Dichloroethane 1,2
Salmonella spp.	Benzene
Trichloroethene	Hexachlorobutadiene
Carbon tetrachloride	Dichloromethane
Tetrachloroethane	THM (Chloroform)
1,3,5-Trichlorobenzene	THM (Bromoform)
1,2,4- Trichlorobenzene	THM (Bromodichloromethane)
1,2,3- Trichlorobenzene	THM (Dibromochloromethane)

For the implementation of the pilot-plant in Demosite 3, a series of national and European regulations related to the use of water and wastewater discharges were taken into account. During the pilot-plant operation, increasing the percentage of reused water in the WWTP and improving the quality of treated effluent were the main goals, which had been previously defined based on these policy documents:

- Council Directive 91/271/EEC in terms of urban waste treatment (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/1991/271/oj>)
- Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on minimum requirements for water reuse (2018) (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52018PC0337>) – Regulation (EU) 2020/741.
- Water reuse: RD1620/2007 (<https://boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2007-21092>) where the juridical regime for the reuse of treated waters is established.

At **national level**, these official documents, which affect Almendralejo WWTP and surrounding areas, have been considered:

- National Hydrologic Plan (https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/agua/temas/planificacionhidrologica/Ley112005modificacionphn_tcm30-98556.pdf). Project for hydric management at the national level, where different aspects for coordination of the river basins are observed together with general measures for the good use of the water resources.
- National Plan for Water Reutilization (https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/agua/participacionpublica/version_preliminar_pnra231210_tcm30-136850.pdf). New tool for water management, in order to ensure water supply and to improve water use by means of replacements of use of new waters with use of regenerated waters.
- Agreement on Cooperation for the protection and sustainable management of waters in the Spanish-Portuguese River Basins (https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/agua/legislacion/acuerdodetolouse_tcm30-136567.pdf). Aimed at joint protection and use of the shared basins so that the good quality of water and current and future usages, are guaranteed.
- Guadiana Hydrologic Plan (<http://planhidrologico2015.chguadiana.es/?planhidrologico2015=lomfrihc5lotqo03uaiknnde43&url=documentos+del+plan+plan+hidrol%F3gico+2016-2021&corp=planhidrologico2015&lang=es&mode=view>). Main management instrument of waters at the basin level (Guadiana basin) aimed at correct development of water politics in the member states.

In relation with the water characteristics in this particular area, the normative determined minimum requirements for the general effluent discharges in terms of SS, BOD₅, COD, P and N (Council Directive 91/271/EEC) and also for additional specific microbiological characteristics (Regulation of the European Parliament on water reuse - Regulation (EU) 2020/741) originated in the risk water evaluation in Almendralejo. Corresponding to these minimum requirements, **Table 3** collects limit values accepted for each measured parameter according to mentioned regulations.

Table 3. Minimum requirements for general effluent discharges according to Council Directive 91/271/EEC and Regulation (EU) 2020/741

Parameter		Directive 91/271/EEC	Regul. (EU) 2020/741
SS	mg/l	35	<10 (*) 35 (> 10,000 pe) 60 (2,000 – 10,000 pe)
COD	mg/l	125	
BOD ₅	mg/l	25	<10 (*) 25 (**)
TN	mg/l	15 (<100,000 pe) 10 (>100,000 pe)	
TP	mg/l	2 (<100,000 pe) 1 (>100,000 pe)	

Turbidity	NTU	<5
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	cfu/100ml	<10 (*) <100 (**) <1000 (***)
<i>Legionella spp.</i>	cfu/l	<1000

* The quality of water reused will be at least these values for certain crops (Category A)

** The quality of water reused will be at least these values for garden and street watering, watering certain crops (Category B)

*** The quality of water reused will be at least these values for garden and street watering, watering certain other crops (Category C)

In parallel with complying with the applicable legal documents, the objective of Demosite 3 is to remove 80% of targeted emerging pollutants, namely Bisphenol A (endocrine disruptor), Terbutylazine (herbicide), selected pharma (Tramadol and 4-Acetylaminoantipyrine) and disinfection by-products (Acetophenone).

2.4 Introduction of the selected train of technologies

The proposed technological solution was projected in the surroundings of Almendralejo due to the existing improvement opportunities, related to the generation of high-quality water ready for reuse, to the protection of the WWTP, and to the convergence with the upcoming regulations, making water completely safe for reuse. Demosite 3 harbours a modular treatment system, **Mobile3Tech**, which integrates three different technologies for the elimination of contaminants and quality improvement of treated water. Although industrial discharges/spills are becoming less frequent, national and European regulations highlight and demand an enhancement in water quality (with a continuously monitoring of certain parameters) and treated water reuse, with the aim of achieving a transition towards circular economy of the integral water cycle. In addition, **Mobile3Tech** requires a very low investment for its implementation, being economically suitable and mobile, being able to be replicated in any interested location with minimal environmental impact.

Therefore, the **Mobile3Tech** pilot plant (schematically depicted in **Figure 3**) has been designed with two goals, namely:

1. In case of an industrial discharge entry into the WWTP, it can be diverted to the mobile module connected to the lamination tank, using effective processes for the spill treatment avoiding the possible damage of the WWTP of Almendralejo plant or its direct discharge to the aquatic environment.
2. Continuously treating incoming water to obtain a quality improved water (while at the same time complies with regulations in place), free of microorganisms and contaminants (reduction of 80%), which can be safely reused. The module is connected at the end of WWTP and works as a tertiary unit in order to ensure physicochemical and microbiological values established by regulations.

Figure 3. General scheme of WWTP of Almendralejo with Mobile3Tech integration

The technologies involved within the **Mobile3Tech** unit are designed as three different integrated modules:

- **Advanced control unit.** The objective of this module is the rapid and continuous detection of the biotoxicity of WWTP input water flow, where potential industrial spill can be detected. This advanced control unit allows to decide if there is not a spill in the input flow, and hence the influent can be treated by the conventional biological reactor at WWTP or, on the contrary, there's a spill in such a way that an additional advanced oxidation process is necessary. This unit allows measurements to be made online. If the degree of toxicity is high, the influent is directed to the proposed advanced oxidation treatment. Otherwise, if the control unit considers that input flow does not present biological hazard to treatment plant, the influent follows its usual course towards the conventional biological reactor. This module has been provided by Technion, and the system unit is based on the determination of the toxicity relating it to the bioluminescence generated by a bacterium, proportional to the stress it suffers when coming into contact with toxic substances.
- **Advanced Adsorption.** If the advanced control unit doesn't detect high biotoxicity in the influent, the **Mobile3Tech** unit treats the water flow at the end of the WWTP, acting as a tertiary treatment. This module consists of the removal of contaminants by adsorption with granular activated carbon (GAC), as well as with powder activated carbon. Interestingly, the pilot includes the innovation of a subsequent system of in-situ photochemical regeneration (described below). This unit can be adapted to variable loads of pollutants, with the advantage of promoting the regeneration of activated carbon, since conventional adsorption technologies require external regeneration. This unit has been upscaled by SOCAMEX according to laboratory assays provided by CNRS. Activated carbon regeneration occurs by photochemical processes, improving the removal of contaminants and reducing operating costs. Normally, activated carbon is disposed as a hazardous waste (managed in landfills), in such a way that the proposed adsorption-regeneration method presents an advantage over the traditional process.

- **Photo-Fenton.** The regeneration of the activated carbon and the pollutants desorbed from activated carbon at advanced adsorption processes are treated by photo-Fenton technique, due to the high effectiveness of this process for the removal of recalcitrant contaminants to biological treatment. Fenton process is based on hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet\text{OH}$) generation, high reactive species, using H_2O_2 and iron salts as reaction promoters. This unit have been upscaled by SOCAMEX according to laboratory assays provided by UPV.

A general scheme of the **Mobile3Tech** module is depicted in **Figure 4**.

Figure 4. Scheme of the Mobile3tech unit deployed at the WWTP of Almendralejo

3 The Mobile3Tech module

The **Mobile3Tech** has been installed within the WWTP of Almendralejo using a container on a 3x5 m area as a work station where all the main equipment has been placed. For security reasons, some parts, as reagents tanks, have been placed outside the container, together with the decanter for treated water. The outside module parts (**Figure 5**) were defined as:

- 2 deposits of 5m³ used to mix and prepare the required reactions.
- 1 deposit of 20m³ to store the clean water after filtration. and a decanter used to recuperate the active carbon
- Reagent tanks for the advanced oxidation reaction.
- Hypochlorite reagent tank for disinfection of treated water.

Figure 5: Final appearance of Mobile3Tech module

The inside of the work station was equipped with a control panel and a computer where the main operator of the plant can track and control every part of the process. In addition, all the probes controllers and flow meters were installed within the main parts of each operation line in order to control the flow through and water characteristics.

For the sake of feasibility and simplicity, the main experiments to carry out with **Mobile3Tech** have been split into three different, but integrated, lines of work (namely: those carried out with the filtration with granular activated carbon module; those carried out with the regeneration of granular activated carbon module; and those realised with the advanced control unit), which are described below.

3.1 Filtration with granular activated carbon module

The water output stream from the WWTP is pumped towards a granulated activated carbon (GAC) filter from the storage chamber of the WWTP. An additional filter is placed before the GAC filter so that high suspended solids input flow do not saturate the GAC filter. A valve box also serves the filter for opening or closing valves depending on the saturation level. The treated water is stored into a 20 m³ tank for its reuse. This process is supported by a pump, which guarantee proper transportation of treated water to the deposit for its final use. General characteristics of the main elements of the active carbon filter are displayed below (**Figure 6** and **Table 4**).

Figure 6. Advanced adsorption filter (GAC)

Table 4. Technical specifications of filtration module

ADVANCED ADSORPTION MODULE	
S _{filtration} (m ²)	0.28
H _{GAC} (m)	1.0
Flow rate (m ³ /h)	0.8-1.6

The filtration line has an average energy expense of 3.43 KWh/day (with a cost of 0.29678 €/kWh, this results in a little more than 1 € per day in energy) and a downtime of 1h if cleaning needs to be done.

3.2 Regeneration of granular activated carbon module

This line of work is focused on the regeneration of the saturated carbon from the filtration line using Photo-Fenton as selected oxidation process. This unit allows to give GAC more life cycles, saving costs and reducing wastes, contributing to the circular economy of water and the materials associated to its treatment and management.

This module uses stored water coming from the output stream of the WWTP. The influent is then mixed with the necessary reagents and adjusted to an optimum pH level, ensuring the proper conditions to regenerate the carbon. The acidic aqueous mixture is sent to a second tank using a pump, where the saturated active carbon is added. Finally, the content is pumped to a decanter flowing through the advanced oxidation unit. Photo-Fenton unit uses LEDs in order to provide the water stream with the right radiation conditions to make possible the active carbon regeneration.

Excess water is recirculated for future cycles. Simultaneously, carbon is recovered, filtered and dried for its analysis. Characteristics of the main elements of the advanced oxidation system are displayed below (**Figure 7** and **Table 5**).

Figure 7. Details of advanced oxidation unit (Photo-Fenton)

Table 5. Technical specifications of Photo-Fenton module

ADVANCED OXIDATION MODULE	
Sort of light	LED
P (kW)	1.50
Flow rate (m ³ /h)	5

In this unit, the reagent costs based in their consumption are about 0.5 € per cycle, confirming the low investment and daily cost of this advanced oxidation module.

3.3 Advanced control unit

This unit has been provided by Technion (Israel Institute of Technology), and is based on the use of specific bacteria in order to quickly detect and decide about the presence toxic compounds.

The unit has a minimal energy cost. The advanced control module uses a specific dye along with the bacteria and the water sample to detect the colour change once the influent is in contact with the microorganisms. This variation provides a signal that can be related and translated into toxicity levels.

Water from the input stream of the WWTP is pumped to the unit, where the bacteria are maintained at the optimum temperature, and then taken through the different phases of the unit by means of 5 small pumps. Once the operation concludes, the unit uses these same 5 small pumps to wash the system and the residue is collected in a specific container and properly managed. Final installation of the advanced control unit in **Mobile3Tech** container is shown in **Figure 8**.

Figure 8. Advanced control unit module for toxicity detection (Advanced control unit)

4 Testing report

4.1 Testing campaign description

This section of the Deliverable 5.5 includes the testing campaign proposed and carried out to validate the operation of the treatment lines and optimize their operation. In order to obtain clear data for the functioning of each of the units of the module, trials to be performed were divided according to the 3 process lines described in section 3 of this Deliverable, which can operate independently.

4.1.1 Filtration with granular activated carbon

The objective of the trials with the advanced adsorption unit was to evaluate the efficacy and reliability of the filtration with granular activated carbon as a tertiary treatment for the removal of emerging pollutants, guaranteeing and improving the quality of water for reuse. Having in mind the current legislation, this **Mobile3Tech** unit is also aimed to reduce microbiological and physicochemical parameters until mandatory values for water reutilization.

In addition to the testing plan of Demosite 3, the global emergency situation due to the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic added new goals for this module. The efficiency of **Mobile3Tech** was also tested for the **abatement of SARS-CoV-2 in wastewater** at real scale, addressed in project Ô also in WP11. Since conventional WWTP processes have been proved not to completely abate this virus in some cases, filtration with granular activated carbon appears as a promising alternative for the removal of SARS-CoV-2, achieving not only an appropriate treated water quality, but ensuring public health. In this sense, samples from this module (Input and Output water samples) were also analyzed for COVID-19 detection, as well as samples from the influent of Almendralejo WWTP.

Table 6 shows the measured parameters that were analyzed from the input and output stream of the active carbon filter to achieve **Mobile3Tech** objectives. **Table 7**, on its part, displays the dates when samples were collected. Additional physico-chemical parameters are also measured, although they are not compulsory, for a better monitoring of water quality.

Table 6. Analytic parameters – Sampling for filtration with GAC module

Parameter	SAMPLES COLLECTION	
	Filtration module INPUT	Decanter treated water OUTPUT
COD	X	X
BOD₅ (Regulation 2020/741)	X	X
COT	X	X
TSS (Regulation 2020/741 and RD 1720/2007)	X	X
Nitrates	X	X
Total N	X	X
Total P	X	X
VOCs	X	X
Emerging pollutants	X	X
SARS-CoV-2	X	X
Escherichia coli (Regulation 2020/741 and RD 1720/2007)	X	X
Clostridium perfringens	X	X
Salmonella spp. (RD 1720/2007)	X	X
Legionella spp. (Regulation 2020/741: < 1000 CFU/L and RD 1720/2007)	X	X
Total Colliphages	X	X
Intestinal nematodes (Regulation 2020/741: ≤ 1 egg/L; RD 1620/2007: 1 egg/10L)	X	X
Turbidity (Regulation 2020/741 y RD 1720/2007)	X	X
pH	X	X

Some parameters analysed are followed by the current regulation and normative (in brackets) which determine minimum requirements for the general effluent discharges.

Table 7. Dates when the samples were collected

SAMPLE DATES (mm/dd/yyyy)			
07-27-2022	08-08-2022	08-31-2022	10-13-2022
08-01-2022	08-10-2022	09-14-2022	10-26-2022
08-03-2022	08-17-2022	09-28-2022	11-09-2022

4.1.2 Regeneration of granular activated carbon

The pilot plant is prepared to regenerate the active carbon from the filter once it has been saturated. In order to evaluate the efficacy of the active carbon regeneration and optimization potential of the process, different variables were taken in account:

- Quantity of activated carbon

- Percentage of intensity applied regarding the maximum available on the FENTON controller
- Number of regeneration cycles

In this sense, the assays were planned with the variation of these aforementioned variables, as well as the sampling dates when the experiments were carried out. Samples were sent to CNRS for their analysis and porosity determination, together with the initial GAC used for this purpose. All these Data were collected in **Table 8**:

Table 8. Trial variables and sampling of Photo-Fenton module

	Flow (m ³ /h)	Cycles of treatment	GAC concentration category	Radiation intensity category	Sample Dates (mm/dd/yyyy)
Trial 1	3.5	1	low concentration	maximum	10-05-2022
Trial 2	3.5	1	low concentration	medium	10-07-2022
Trial 3	3.5	1	low concentration	low	11-04-2022
Trial 4	3.5	1	high concentration	maximum	10-11-2022
Trial 5	3.5	1	high concentration	medium	10-10-2022
Trial 6	3.5	1	high concentration	low	11-04-2022
Trial 7	3.5	2	low concentration	maximum	11-09-2022
Trial 8	3.5	2	low concentration	medium	11-10-2022

4.1.3 Advanced control unit

The Advanced control unit provided by Technion is fed with wastewater from the Almendralejo WWTP's pretreatment outlet, with the objective of detecting possible toxic loads in the water. In order to establish a correct relation among bioluminescence detected by the Module and the presence of pollutants and undesirable discharges, a train of experiments was carried out, in which the parameters depicted in **Table 9** were analysed (and always according to policy and law requirements as described in **Table 5**) in the search for correlations of bioluminescence and the other parameters defined. Even though some of the main components of the spills in the area were analysed as well, they have been finally removed from the deliverable because the analytic method has not allowed the reliable quantification of them. Once the advanced control unit was operating in a continuous mode, several samples were put in contact with microorganisms for luminescence detection in order to check the module decision making. These samples were also analysed with the same physicochemical parameters of **Table 9**, for checking if the signal of the bacteria corresponds to the characteristics of the water introduced in terms of contaminants concentration, hence validating the goodness of the system for the specific water of Almendralejo WWTP.

Table 9. Analytic parameters for advanced control unit

PARAMETERS	
COD	Turbidity
BOD ₅	pH
TOC	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
Total N	<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>
Total P	<i>Legionella spp.</i>

VOCs	Total Colliphages
Emerging pollutants	SARS-CoV-2
BIOLUMINESCENCE Signal	

4.2 Data report

In this section of the Deliverable 5.5, the most relevant results obtained in different technologies of **Mobile3Tech** module are collected and explained in order to confirm the proper operation of the technologies proposed in Demosite 3. In this sense, the results aimed to evaluate the efficiency of the whole process and to allow the module optimization. Data section are divided according to the established methods of operation: filtration with granular activated carbon for treated water reuse, regeneration of the granular activated carbon and toxic spill detection by advanced control unit.

4.2.1 Filtration with granular activated carbon

The main goal of this module consists in evaluating the effectiveness and reliability of activated carbon filtration process as a tertiary treatment to guarantee the quality and safety of the water for reuse. In this sense, values obtained during entire operating time must conform to the current regulations. In addition, the efficiency of granular activated carbon in the retention of emerging compounds and SARS-CoV-2 through a continuous filtration process is analysed.

A broad study of emerging pollutants existent in Almendralejo WWTP has been reported for 5 different compounds: Bisphenol A (endocrine disruptor), Terbutylazine (herbicide), Tramadol (analgesic compound), 4-Acetylaminoantipyrine (metabolite of an analgesic and antipyretic drug) and Acetophenone (perfume and disinfection industry).

These emerging pollutants concentration was analysed at the input and output water sampling points of advanced adsorption module. Although they are all detected by chromatographic methods, the low signal provided in some cases avoids reliable quantification values, despite the fact that a slight elimination is observed (reduction in area of the chromatogram sample peaks).

However, the high concentration of **Tramadol** made it possible to establish the most clear conversion values for the elimination of this pharmaceutical compound. In this sense, this contaminant was selected as model compound to study the removal of pollutants in the adsorption module with granular activated carbon proposed in **Mobile3Tech**. Conversion is defined as the fraction of elimination/reduction of the parameter studied, expressed as a percentage, with respect to that value of the input water to the GAC module.

Figure 9. Conversion values of Tramadol removal at different sampling dates

Figure 10 shows the conversion values reached on the different sampling dates carried out according to the testing plan. An ascendant trend is observed with a maximum of 79.9% of Tramadol removal. These results suggest that the pollutants elimination requires an acclimation time, after which the conversion values reach the goals proposed by the adsorption module.

In the case of **Bisphenol A**, samples taken on days 08/08/2022 and 09/14/2022 let determine its concentration, with conversion values around 25% in both cases. These results confirm the effectiveness of the advanced adsorption module in the removal of emerging contaminants present in wastewater.

Table 10 shows the conversion values achieved for each of the physicochemical or microbiological parameter through water treatment in this **Mobile3Tech** module. The average value of the conversion values obtained are presented. Even though the reduction in the values of such parameters through **Mobile3Tech** was not a main objective of the pilot, it is worth mentioning the reduction achieved.

Table 10. Range of conversion values and average conversion values (%) of parameters analysed at Mobile3Tech module: filtration with GAC.

PARAMETER	CONVERSION (%)	Average (%)
SS	20.0 – 87.5	34.7
COD	23.2 – 70.0	43.5
BOD ₅	40.0 – 91.3	57.9
TOC	7.0 – 26.0	16.0
TN	1.3 – 35.2	12.2
TP	2.7 – 6.8	5.3
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	75.0 – 96.2	83.1

As can be represented in the values shown in **Table 10**, a significant reduction in most parameters is achieved in this treatment with filtration with GAC of the **Mobile3Tech** module. Samples collected at last month shown an increase in nitrogen and phosphorous concentration reduction, which indicates and confirms an acclimation and improvement of the process as the operating time moves forward.

Together with the assays originally planned in Demosite 3, the performance of this module has been tested for the **abatement of SARS-CoV-2** in wastewater at real scale. Conventional treatments applied in WWTP do not guarantee complete removal of SARS-CoV-2 and, therefore, it is desirable to provide additional means in order to achieve the appropriate quality of treated water for reuse. The amount of samples analysed for COVID-19 detection was 36.

For the monitoring of SARS-CoV-2, tests have not only been performed at the input and output sampling point of the Mobile3Tech module, but also influent samples to the WWTP of Almendralejo. In the input water to the WWTP, in all cases (n= 12), the virus was quantified, being evident the presence of SARS-CoV-2 in real wastewaters, which remains affecting public health. Moreover, at the entrance of the **Mobile3Tech** module of filtration with GAC, still a few samples (n= 5) contained SARS-CoV-2, validating the recalcitrant behaviour of the virus. After treated with filtration with GAC, the absence of positive results (none of the samples contained SARS-CoV-2) indicates the SARS-CoV-2 was efficiently removed with the adsorption technology of **Mobile3Tech**.

The treatment implanted within Demosite 3 allows the complete removal of this virus, since no presence of SARS-CoV-2 was detected in the whole operating time, testing not only the filtration module with additional goals, but achieving a highly purified treated water without risks for the population, ready for its reuse.

4.2.2 Regeneration of the granular activated carbon

The pilot plant of Demosite 3 has been designed in order to allow the regeneration treatment of granular activated carbon once it could have reduce its retention capacity and could be saturated. As described in Section 3.2, the regeneration process consists of an advanced oxidation treatment in Fenton photo-reactor. The optimal operating pH conditions are achieved previous to operation and the required reagent doses are calculated for the amount of GAC to be regenerated.

In order to check the effectiveness of the proposed regeneration, initial (fresh) GAC – prior introduction to the filtration module – was analyzed. Specifically, the following parameters were analyzed:

- pH_{PZC}
- S_{BET} (m^2/g). The value of this parameter on fresh samples is 996.
- V_{pores} (cm^3/g)
- $V_{micropores}$ (cm^3/g)
- $V_{narrow-micropore}$ (cm^3/g)

Taking into account the testing plan proposed in Section 4.1.2 of this Deliverable, different GAC regeneration assays have been carried out modifying the amount of carbon treated, the percentage of radiation intensity applied and the flow to be treated.

Results obtained in these advanced oxidation tests are shown in **Figure 11**. As the operating conditions of each assay were previously described, the information has been simplified in order to avoid duplicated data.

Figure 10. BET surfaces of regeneration assays at different conditions

Figure 11 shows the average values of the surface BET area obtained for the assays performed, in comparison with the values of the fresh GAC and the carbon extracted from the saturated filters. Selecting a low GAC concentration, after its treatment in the advanced oxidation module, the results obtained acquired values close to the surface BET area belonging to fresh GAC. It can be concluded that this process is effective for the regeneration.

On the other hand, if the concentration of saturated GAC increased up to a high concentration, a downward trend was observed in the recovery of the carbon activity related to the reduction in the radiation used. By increasing this concentration value, the required operating conditions involve a higher cost of the process in the use of reagents and energy to reach optimal results for the treatment.

Additional thermogravimetric analysis indicated that the regeneration has been carried out correctly, since there is no porosity blockage. In addition, in all cases, the volume of micropores with respect to total measured pores was similar to the ratio obtained for fresh GAC, since the high microporosity values are directly related to the high adsorption capacity. Additional assays are required to verify the stability of these activated carbons to successive regeneration cycles. However, these tests are currently being performed in order to achieve optimization of the conditions of the advanced oxidation module.

4.2.3 Advanced control unit

The advanced control unit aims to continuously monitor the toxicity level of the input flow to the WWTP, in order to detect potential toxic loads present in the water. The advanced control unit proposed for this Demosite 3 is based on the reaction of bioluminescence bacteria to the presence of a series of toxic compounds, generating stress in the microorganisms by modifying the luminescent signal.

In order to check the module operation and a correct tuning of the equipment, a relationship between the emitted bioluminescence signal and the presence of contaminants needs to be established. A voltage signal from 0-10 V, expresses the bioluminescent parameter to relate. The parameter selected is the **Conductivity**, due to its easy and rapid detection, together with its well-known relationship with industrial spills for this specific case. The relationship has been described and represented below (**Figure 12**). This graph allows to know the toxicity level (in terms of presence of harmful chemicals) from the voltage displayed by advanced control unit.

Figure 11. Toxicity detection (%) vs Conductivity at advanced control unit

Figure 12 shows the results, expressed as percentage of toxicity of the advanced control unit. Describing a trend line between samples within the established maximum and minimum detection limits, the adjustment indicated that the advanced control unit is valid for measuring the toxicity of a sample, setting the % of toxicity vs conductivity relationship with a very high fitting.

Subsequently, in order to validate the operation of the module, three different influents from the Almendralejo WWTP were collected on different dates and passed through the advanced detection unit. It was observed that low conductivity values matched a zero (%) toxicity of the samples. It can be concluded that, on the whole, the system is reliable in order to detect spills in the area, providing an extra value to the pilot.

5 Conclusions

The train of technologies proposed for its implementation in Demosite 3 has been validated with the results obtained in each of the parts that make up the **Mobile3Tech** module: advanced adsorption with granular activated carbon, advanced oxidation process and a continuous detection of toxicity by means of an advanced control module.

At this point, a summary of the results obtained can be compared with the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) established in the **Project Ô** (Deliverable D6.1). Each of the parameters will be explained to obtain a final overview of whether the **Mobile3Tech** module meets the proposed objectives.

- In terms of BOD₅, COD, SS and *Legionella spp*, the values obtained at the output sampling point of the filtration module meet the mentioned KPIs. In all the samples analysed, only in a very few cases the value of SS and BOD₅ slightly exceed the limits set for water reuse (but within water discharge values), which may be due to the high value obtained in influent analysis at the same sampling date. Nevertheless, the advanced adsorption module using granular activated carbon appears as an effective solution in reducing physicochemical and microbiological parameters.
- In the case of total N, total P and *Escherichia coli*, the results obtained at the end of the process need to be improved in order to comply with the established KPIs. The concentration of both N and P at the entrance to the module is higher than the value observed when preliminary study and design was carried out (year 2018). Despite this, the elimination of both parameters is observed, in such a way that it is possible that the elimination will improve after some time for acclimation of the system, as has been discussed in this deliverable.
- Finally, the preliminary study of the emerging contaminants present in the wastewaters of Almendralejo established a list of compounds needed to be eliminated according to the KPIs. The screening carried out just prior to the final installation of the **Mobile3Tech** module resulted in the presence of different pollutants and the absence of some of the proposed ones. Therefore, the list of emerging contaminants was updated with the selected compounds to be eliminated, being those described in section 2.2 of this Deliverable the ones finally selected. The pharmaceutical compound which offered best possibilities (owing to its greater abundance and hence accuracy of the quantification process) is **Tramadol**, with output values from the filtration module which meet those initially set as the objective of the Project (ca. 80%). However, the concentration of this pollutant observed at the influent is 20 times higher than that detected when the KPIs were established. In the case of **terbuthylazine**, the value established as suitable for the reuse of treated water is 0.02 (KPIs). The chromatographic analysis of the output samples did not provide significant results because the equipment's detection limit for this compound is 0.03. Though, in all the samples analyzed, the concentration of terbuthylazine was lower

than the mentioned DL, it could be assumed that this herbicide complied with the defined KPIs.

To conclude, the technologies proposed in the **Mobil3Tech** offer an effective and low-cost solution for allowing a high quality of the waters to be reused. The continuous control of the water steam allows optimization of the entire treatment process together with a reduction of costs and waste through the advanced adsorption module coupling with regeneration of activated carbon.